

Building meaningful connections with large online classes

Yuhui Gao

DCU Business School, Dublin City University, Ireland.

Abstract

As we adapt to the sudden shift to online teaching caused by the Covid-19 pandemic and discover new pedagogical possibilities in this medium, building meaningful connections in large online classes in order to foster effective learning continues to present its challenges. The objective of this paper is to reflect some key lessons learned from teaching large classes online. Four perspectives are presented: upskilling through professional development, creating meaningful learning experiences by embedding citizen scholars through curriculum and assessment design, balancing online pedagogical care and self-care, and promoting a learning community among students.

Keywords: Covid-19; large online classes; meaningful connections

1. Introduction

Educators have expressed their concern that ‘online teaching is often perceived as incapable of fostering the necessary interpersonal relationships or sense of classroom community that leads to effective student learning’ (Deacon, 2012, p.5). This concern is further intensified in the light of the sudden transition to online teaching and learning as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, in which many educators have faced the simultaneous challenges of shifting to online delivery with little remote teaching experience, an issue compounded by the demands of large classes.

As Deacon (2012, p.9) points out, ‘effective online instruction requires teachers to become literate in not only the intellectual dynamics of teaching and learning in virtual environments, but the affective and social dynamics, as well’. Inspired by this insight, the present paper reflects on some key lessons learned from teaching large online classes during the pandemic. The reflection draws upon the experiences of (a) upskilling through professional development, (b) creating meaningful learning experiences by embedding societal awareness and participation through curriculum and assessment design, (c) balancing online pedagogical care and self-care, and (d) promoting a learning community among students. The paper concludes that effective online learning can be nurtured, even in large classes, by building meaningful connections in situations where students are presented with opportunities to engage with the module content, society, and fellow peer students.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

The module was delivered to over 250 undergraduate business students at Dublin City University (DCU) and was moved online in the autumn of 2020. The timing of this online teaching coincided with the emerging economic impact of Covid-19 on Irish businesses, especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Given that Irish SMEs account for 99.8% of the total number of enterprises and 46.2% of total business turnover (Central Statistics Office, 2018) in Ireland, the contribution of SMEs to the Irish economy is very important. In that context, the manner in which Irish SMEs respond to fast-moving business environments caused by the pandemic has become an urgent issue. One of the aims of the module was to encourage students to engage with their local SMEs to offer them a number of marketing insights by carrying out a marketing research project on their behalf, thus enhancing the students’ understanding of how marketing information can be used to assist organisations in diagnosing, evaluating, and solving real marketing issues.

3. Literature Review

Guided by the existing literature (e.g., Arvanitakis & Hornsby, 2016; Deacon, 2012; Farrell & Logan, 2020; Hornsby, 2020; Rose & Adams, 2014), four aspects of the literature were drawn in this paper. First, professional development is recognised as a vital component of strategies to enhance the quality of teaching and learning and to promote educators' self-efficacy (Buczynski & Hansen, 2010). The abrupt shift to online classes caused by the pandemic has generated an immediate need for educators to upskill themselves in terms of their online pedagogical approaches and to embrace the use of different tools and technologies. Relevant online teaching webinars, workshops, and publications have mushroomed at institutional, national, and international levels in a short space of time (e.g., HBPE, 2021; Watermeyer et al., 2021). Educators' learning needs have also now evolved from the initial 'last minute learning before teaching' to more targeted workshops to further enhance the quality of teaching. Professional development and training workshops have played a significant role in ensuring a smooth switch from physical classrooms to online classes. Without this timely training, educators would probably lack confidence in managing online classes, as well as in motivating students' engagement by using a variety of approaches and techniques.

Second, Arvanitakis and Hornsby (2016) have developed a citizen scholar framework where both scholarship and actively engaged citizens can be embedded in pedagogical strategies. The citizen scholar framework directs students towards their responsibilities as citizens in their communities (Hornsby, 2020). Active engagement in communal (societal) problems gives students a motivation to learn, a purpose to carry out the coursework, and a desire to be a citizen scholar. Educators are encouraged to foster learning environments in which attributes of citizen scholars such as resilience, adaptability, and ethical leadership can be developed (Arvanitakis & Hornsby 2016). As Hornsby (2020, p.3) suggests, 'It is within the power of a lecturer to organiz[s]e these spaces to be meaningful experiences', even during the pandemic when most large classes moved online.

Third, the 'ethic of care' has been identified as central to the practice of teaching (Noddings, 2003). The ethos of care of the online learning approach has also been advocated in the literature (e.g., Hornsby, 2020; Robinson et al., 2017). It has further been suggested that students' perceptions of the context of care in the classroom environment can have an impact on their motivation and behaviour (McLeod, 1997). For example, students tend to feel empowered to ask questions, participate in class and be self-motivated if they feel confident and comfortable in the classroom setting (Deacon, 2012; McLeod, 1997). Creating online pedagogical care is even more relevant as we move to virtual teaching, as a recent student survey shows that nearly 80% of students reported issues with motivation during the pandemic (USI, 2020). However, when the online learning environment is 'open for business' 24/7, the tension between care for students and self-care has never been greater

(Rose & Adams, 2014). A recent study has found that working from home has been considered as a significant contributor to workload intensification and an interruption of work-life balance (Watermeyer et al., 2021). Though educators have shared some useful practices to ease the conflicting demands of home care responsibilities and the provision of pastoral care for students (e.g., FAQ sheets, online synchronous office hours or drop-ins, email hours, discussion forums, teaching assistant support etc.), research into the nature and role of care in online teaching and learning remains limited (Rose & Adams, 2014).

Fourth, educators have noted that, since many students ‘may be missing the connections of being physically on campus or having informal chats in the halls and over coffee; a positive online community can help’ (HBPE, 2021, p.20). This notion is in line with a recent student survey of the pandemic learning experience, which shows that 36% of students reported having no opportunities to engage with other students through their online learning, and 78% listed peer support as one of the main sources of support for them during the pandemic (USI, 2020). Learning is recognised as a social process, but the social and emotional components of online teaching have been largely neglected in the literature (Deacon, 2012). Online learning communities can only be *communal* rather than *virtual* if they can create a feeling of connectedness, and a sense of belonging and togetherness (Deacon 2012; Foster 1997). A number of useful practices to help create a sense of community and opportunities for students to engage with their peers have been suggested by educators (e.g., actively making time for community, establishing clear community norms for a virtual environment, discussion forums, informal ‘hallway’ conversations, listening etc.).

4. Reflection on Implications for Practice

Moving to online teaching as a result of the pandemic has been challenging; that challenge is heightened when large classes are involved. The objective of this paper has been to reflect on some key lessons learned through large online classes, drawing upon the following lessons: participating in professional teaching development and training, embedding citizen scholars through course design, and attending to the *affective* and *social* needs of learning. As Figure 1 illustrates, building meaningful connections with students can be achieved through three parallel approaches with the pillar support of educators’ commitment to continuous professional development. Some reflective notes on practices are also provided below.

Figure 1. Building meaningful connections with large online classes

Lesson one: *Surfing the sea of online teaching related workshops and professional development programmes.* Global educators have compiled and shared new and emerging best remote teaching practices (e.g., DCU teaching online resource bank, Harvard Business Publishing Education teaching resources). Many educators have upskilled their digital competencies by attending workshops on different teaching platforms, breakout rooms, polls, Vevox, H5P, and various students' online engagement activities. As we are committed to continuous professional development, we might be tempted to try as many engagement tools as possible to maintain students' curiosity and interests, but we need to be mindful that each tool is used to maximise the achievement of the module learning outcomes, not for purposes of entertainment. In the meantime, the sheer volume of online teaching materials can be overwhelming. We must learn to surf but not to drown in the sea of these workshops and materials. As the old saying goes, *do one thing at a time*. Engaging in professional development afforded me the opportunity to explore a range of digital tools to use in my module. However, I used only those I believed supported and enhanced the teaching and learning experience in this large class context.

Lesson two: *Encouraging citizen scholars through course design and assessment strategies.* The project-based module was designed for students to work with local SMEs to carry out a marketing research project to help identify and solve some pressing marketing issues. Students were provided with an opportunity to exercise themselves as citizen scholars (Arvanitakis & Hornsby, 2016) by collaborating with businesses. In total, students engaged with nearly 50 local SMEs with an individual project completion rate of 99%. One of the challenging elements of this project during the pandemic was to carry out most of the primary research remotely (e.g., via Zoom interviews). This purpose-driven assignment motivated

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students to embrace these challenges through the aspiration of helping their communities. Students also further developed their client management skills, raised their ethical research awareness, and quickly adapted to new ways of conducting research, all of which are important attributes of citizen scholars (Arvanitakis & Hornsby, 2016).

Lesson three: *Balancing online pedagogical care and self-care*. It remains very challenging to attend to the needs of a large number of students online in a work-from-home environment (Watermeyer et al., 2021). A few practices worked well for this module. For example, a weekly dedicated drop-in clinic was created to address any queries and to calm any anxious students; an FAQ sheet was compiled and made available online for students to consult; there were clear communications with the students regarding email hours and the expected response timeframe; and additional teaching resources such as support from a dedicated teaching assistant was also a great help.

Lesson four: *Fostering a sense of community among students*. Effort was made in this module to encourage a sense of togetherness. For instance, there were some informal check-in conversations before the start of the lecture; a Vevox word cloud exercise was conducted to establish how students were feeling during the mid-term; and an informal Q&A session was held at the end of each class. Discussion forums were also used in another large online class where students were required to evaluate and provide constructive feedback on other groups' work. This exercise triggered rich interactive discussions among the students. The communal learning further fostered a sense of connectivity and togetherness by the students helping each other.

In conclusion, many of us have at different stages felt overwhelmed by the significant number of new protocols that we have to learn and adapt to in this domain. With an open mind toward continuous pedagogical improvement, a caring attitude and a duty of responsibility to our students, however, making meaningful connections with students, even in large online classes, is not mission impossible. As we continue to tackle the challenges and discover new possibilities of online or hybrid teaching, we also need to recognise that we are only human beings and that we are trying our best. As Farrell and Logan (2020, p.37) note, educators should 'allow imperfection to be part of the classroom environment and convey the 'real' you in the asynchronous teaching space'. Ultimately, the goal of moving online is 'not to replicate a face-to-face classroom, but to optimiz[s]e your course for a rich, interactive learning experience' (HBPE, 2021, p.46). By considering the four elements of the module as described above, I hope that I can claim with confidence and pride that the experience of managing large online classes has made me a better educator.

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